

Empowering Persons with Disabilities for Creating a Better Society: A Study of District Jhang, Pakistan

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the importance of Empowering Persons with Disabilities (PWDs) for creating a Better Society in District Jhang. The main objectives of this research are to explore the ways through which PWDs are empowered in Jhang. Moreover, it examines the changes experienced by PWDs due to their empowerment and explores how the empowerment of PWDs contributes to the creation of a better society. This research is qualitative in nature and based on a descriptive research design. Data has been collected through semi-structured interviews. The target population from where the sample was selected was the persons with various types of disabilities, family members of PWDs, and representatives of the Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal Department working for the empowerment of PWDs in District Jhang. The sample was selected by using purposive sampling, and some cases were also recruited through snowball sampling. Furthermore, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the data. The results of this study indicate that the situation of PWDs in District Jhang has significantly improved and is somewhat different, as they have a relatively better position in society compared to others. In this sense, these individuals can earn their livelihood independently and have increased participation and integration in society. The credit for improving the lives of PWDs goes to the Social Welfare & Bait ul Maal Department, Community organisations, families of PWDs, and the receptive and supportive community.

INTRODUCTION

Disability is increasingly recognised not solely as a medical issue but as a complex interaction between health conditions and environmental or societal barriers that limit full participation in society. Globally, over 1.3 billion people, approximately 16% of the world's population, live with some form of disability. This figure reflects systemic challenges, including inadequate healthcare access, stigma, limited educational and employment opportunities, and policy inaction, particularly in developing countries (Organization, 2022). The spectrum of disabilities is diverse, including physical, visual, intellectual, and hearing impairments, and may be visible or invisible, temporary or permanent. Poverty, lack of healthcare systems, and poor infrastructure of education all contribute to the compounding of disability in low and middle-income countries (Al Shami & Nashwan, 2025).

According to Altman (2014), Disability is an impairment, an activity limitation, and a restriction in participation. Disability is not only a medical challenge but also a social one, shaped and maintained by environmental and attitudinal obstacles that restrict the full involvement of Persons with Disabilities (PWDs) in society (An, 2024). The medical model considers disability as a diagnosis and treatment issue, while the social model emphasises exclusionary policies, discriminatory norms, and inaccessible infrastructure (Brinkman et al., 2023). The rights-based approach, inspired by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, emphasizes inclusion, equity, and empowerment (Broderick, 2015). In Pakistan, census figures show wide variation. The Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2017) recorded 0.48% of the population as persons with disabilities (1,643,286 individuals). The 2023 census identified

0.86% (921,347 persons), including 558,775 men and 362,572 women. Differences across censuses reflect changing definitions, data collection methods, and underreporting. Social stigma, limited awareness, and structural barriers also contribute to low registration rates (Ocran, 2022).

In Jhang, a total of 13,505 persons with disabilities were registered on the Disability Management Information System (DPMIS). They were predominantly recorded with physical impairments (9,419), hearing impairments (1,780), visual impairments (1,438), and intellectual impairments (761). The data also highlights a significant gender disparity, with males constituting 67.5% (9,117) and females 32.5% (4,387) of the PWD population, alongside one transgender individual. Regarding employment capacity, 27.3% (3,691) of PWDs are classified as fit to work, while 72.6% (9,800) are not fit, illustrating the need for targeted rehabilitation and vocational programs. Since April 2022, 8,205 new PWDs have been registered, showing increasing coverage by the Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal Department, Punjab. This information is sourced from the official Punjab Social Welfare Department portal's DPMIS, providing authoritative and up-to-date statistics crucial for policy and empowerment initiatives in Jhang (SW&BM).

Figure 1: PWD's Dashboard chart result from DPMIS website, (Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal Punjab)

Table 1. Registered Persons with Disabilities in District Jhang

Category	Data
Total registered PWDs	13,505
Physical impairments	69.7% (9,419)
Hearing impairments	13.2% (1,780)
Visual impairments	10.6% (1,438)
Intellectual disabilities	5.6% (761)
Gender	Male: 67.5% (9,117); Female: 32.5% (4,387); Transgender: 1
Work capacity	Fit to work: 27.3% (3,691); Not fit: 72.6% (9,800)
New registrations since April 2022	8,205

Source: Data from Disability Management Information System (DPMIS) Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal Department, Punjab.

Map of District Jhang

District Jhang has a population of over 3 million, spans 8,809 sq. km and lies between the Chenab and Jhelum rivers. It consists of four tehsils: Jhang, Shorkot, Ahmadpur Sial and 18-Hazari, featuring fertile plains, desert and riverine areas. The economy is primarily based on agriculture which includes wheat, sugarcane, rice and cotton as well as sugar mills, rice mills, textile weaving units and dairy/poultry farms.

Literature Review

The argument by Pezdek & Rasiński (2017) is supported by the social and emancipation models of disability, which highlight that it is society's attitude and structure, rather than the disability itself, that lead to exclusion. People with developmental and physical disabilities who are empowered can participate in society and contribute to the community's flourishing. Empowering PWDs worldwide depends partly on community-based programs and disability rights campaigns (Kuipers, 2013). An example is the Progressive Blind Association (PBA) in Jamaica, recognized as a key agent for change in 2005. After its founding at the Salvation Army School for the Blind, the PBA shifted from a charity approach to adopting the social model of disability. This change emphasized that disability should be viewed as a societal issue, not a personal problem, and aimed to remove barriers in laws, attitudes, and society as a whole. The movement's efforts led to lasting improvements and enhanced lives for Jamaicans with disabilities. The Action on Disability and Development (ADD) program aimed to empower people with disabilities and reduce poverty (Naami & Mikey-Iddrisu, 2013).

SHGs assist women with disabilities (WWDs) by providing training, employment opportunities, and access to loans (Mohapatra & Sahoo, 2016). These services boost the

economy and, at the same time, bring social benefits to women by increasing their self-esteem and decreasing their dependence on men within the family. To advocate for their needs, WWDs started forming groups, which enabled them to become leaders and address problems collaboratively (Wade et al., 2020). Several international and national organizations are dedicated to defending the rights and welfare of people with disabilities. According to Shailendrabhai (2023) the Blind People's Association (BPA) in Ahmedabad, India, was established in 1976 and provides comprehensive support to individuals with visual and other disabilities through training, employment assistance, education, and health services. The non-profit considers persons with disabilities as capable of managing their own lives and contributing to society. Thanks to BPA's efforts, hundreds of people have been helped through education, training and job placement.

The UNCRPD (2006) helps to establish guidelines worldwide to promote fairness and inclusion for persons with disabilities (Organization, 2022). All planning and development efforts should incorporate considerations for people with disabilities. Although there has been international progress on disability rights, significant issues persist in the implementation of these rights (Lord et al., 2010). Therefore, PWDs should be included at all levels of development efforts, especially in villages and communities, to ensure their needs are addressed. Despite advancements, many barriers still prevent the empowerment of PWDs. Stigma often leads society to mistreat people with disabilities and causes PWDs to have a poor self-image. A study by Chen & Shu (2012) in Taiwan showed that negative self-image and ID cards provided at school were key factors in alienation among youth with intellectual disabilities. These

individuals are often viewed through the lens of medicine, which reinforces narratives of dependence and hardship. True equality and integration for PWDs can only be achieved if social attitudes and harmful labels are changed.

Misconceptions, lack of knowledge and the common misbelief that individuals with disabilities aren't capable all cause attitudinal discrimination. Because of this, PWDs often become isolated from the community and have limited chances to take part or express themselves. In Jhang and similar rural and conservative areas, these beliefs are often very firmly held, so it is especially important to use education and awareness campaigns as part of any strategy to help women. Environmental discrimination becomes clear when public spaces and services are difficult for people to use. Many places in District Jhang such as roads, buildings and schools, do not have access ramps or lifts which makes it difficult for everyone to participate. This kind of discrimination takes away the freedom, independence and equal treatment in services from people with disabilities (Schirmer & Michailakis, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

Social Model of Disability: This model challenges the traditional medical perspective by framing disability as a result of social, environmental and attitudinal barriers rather than solely an individual's impairment (Rothman, 2014). It is especially relevant in the District of Jhang, where cultural stigma and infrastructural shortcomings are common. Eliminating societal barriers, such as inaccessible public spaces, discriminatory norms, and lack of policy enforcement, is necessary to enable PWDs to participate fully in society. Empowerment Theory views empowerment as both a process and an

outcome, where PWDs become autonomous, confident, and capable of making decisions that affect their lives (Tinta, 2018).

This framework emphasizes capacity building, access to resources, and participatory decision-making. In Jhang's context, empowerment should address both psychological factors such as self-efficacy and awareness and structural issues including access to education, employment and legal rights. Community-Based Rehabilitation (CBR) promotes disability inclusion through community wide involvement and holistic support, such as healthcare, education, livelihood and social integration (Britton, 2020). Given Jhang's rural-urban mix and limited institutional backing, CBR provides a practical approach to empowering PWDs at the local level by utilizing community resources and fostering inclusive development. This integrated framework guides the study to view empowerment not just as individual change but as a dynamic interaction between PWDs and their socio-cultural environment, focusing on removing external barriers and building internal capacities.

Research Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research method because it is well-suited for exploring how individuals with disabilities are empowered to contribute to a better society. A descriptive research design was adopted, focusing on what, how, when, and where, rather than why. This approach provided an overview of the situation and the participants' experiences. Data was gathered from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected through semi-structured interviews with PWDs, their family members, and representatives of the Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal Department, with respondents

encouraged to share their experiences, perceptions, opinions and ideas freely.

The target population consisted of three data collection groups i-e Persons with various types of disabilities who were beneficiaries of the Himmat Card, ADWC Programme and 3% quota employment in District Jhang, family members of PWDs who were unable to communicate directly due to impairments and representatives from the Social Welfare Department including officers and officials. Purposive sampling was used to select participants based on their relevance and the richness of information they provided, while snowball sampling helped recruit cases referred by initial respondents. The sample comprised 32 respondents, including 12 PWDs, 10 family members, and 10 representatives from the Social Welfare Department (four senior officers and six supervisors). Visits were conducted to the Social Welfare Department in Jhang with interviews starting on 15 June 2025 and concluding by the end of July 2025. Interviews lasted 50-55 minutes with Officers and officials of Social welfare & Bait ul Maal Department, 20-25 minutes with PWDs and 40-45 minutes with family members.

All participants provided informed consent, confidentiality was maintained, withdrawal rights were explained and permission for audio recording was obtained. The research was conducted solely for educational and institutional purposes. The data were analyzed thematically using inductive coding and the framework method which included transcription, familiarization, coding, grouping and interpretation.

Results and Discussion

The findings from this study shows that empowering persons with disabilities in District Jhang has multiple aspects and is viewed differently by departmental

representatives, family members of PWDs and PWDs themselves. The results highlight not only the advantages of programs but also the ongoing barriers that still challenge full inclusion.

Table 2: Thematic Analysis of Respondents: Social Welfare Department Representatives, Family Members, and Persons with Disabilities

Respondent Group	Superordinate Theme	Subordinate Theme	Frequency
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Government Initiatives	Himmat Card program	10/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Awareness workshops	8/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		ADWC Programme	10/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Economic Empowerment	Quarterly stipends	10/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Microfinance schemes	7/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Employment placements	6/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Inclusive Services	Accessible schools	8/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Health service access	9/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Transportation facilities	7/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Stakeholder Engagement	Partnerships with NGOs	8/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Community outreach	5/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Resource mobilization	5/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Implementation Barriers	Insufficient funding	6/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Limited staffing	7/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Administrative delays	4/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Public Perception	Greater public empathy	6/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Media awareness campaigns	5/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Positive peer influence	4/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representative	PWD Impact	Entrepreneurial ventures	6/10

s				Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Budget allocation	6/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Volunteering	5/10	Family Members	Reduced Dependency	Economic independence of PWDs	9/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Mentorship roles	4/10	Family Members	Social Acceptance	Better inclusion in community	7/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Personal Growth	Boost in confidence	7/10	Family Members	Caregiving Challenges	Heavy family responsibility	6/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Improved self-image	6/10	Family Members	Support from Government	Himmat Card, assistive devices	8/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Enhanced social ties	5/10	Family Members	Service Gaps	Insufficient financial aid	7/10
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Inspiring Examples	PWD-run enterprises	5/10	Persons with Disabilities (PWDs)	Economic Empowerment	Independent income	10/12
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Recognition by society	5/10	Persons with Disabilities (PWDs)	Community Participation	Involvement in local activities	8/12
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Award-winning stories	3/10	Persons with Disabilities (PWDs)	Confidence & Self-Image	Boost in confidence	7/12
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives	Policy Enhancement	Inclusive legislation	8/10	Persons with Disabilities (PWDs)	Accessibility Challenges	Transport and infrastructure gaps	6/12
Social Welfare Dept. Representatives		Regular monitoring	7/10				

Persons with Disabilities (PWDs)	Social Perceptions	Experiences of stigma	5/12
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Table 2 summarizes the thematic analysis from interviews with Social Welfare Department representatives (n = 10), family members of PWDs (n = 10), and persons with disabilities (PWDs) themselves (n = 12). It presents superordinate themes, subordinate themes and their frequencies, highlighting both commonalities and differences across respondent groups.

Representatives from the Social Welfare Department highlighted both achievements and challenges in their empowerment efforts. A large majority Eight out of ten (80%) emphasized the importance of initiatives like the Himmat Card, distributing assistive devices and providing financial support. Seven out of ten (70%) reported that vocational training programs are helping PWDs gain skills and contribute economically. All four senior officers (100%) pointed out the need for strict enforcement of the 3% job quota reserved for PWDs in public institutions. In contrast, all six supervisors (100%) explained their roles in monitoring field-level implementation. However, respondents also raised concerns about limited budgets, insufficient staffing and a lack of accessible infrastructure which restricts the impact of empowerment policies. This indicates that, although the department plays a central role in promoting empowerment, systemic constraints continue to pose a significant obstacle.

Family members of PWDs reported that empowerment efforts had improved daily life and reduced dependence. Nine out of ten (90%) family members said that government and community programs created opportunities for work and skills development, which eased financial pressure

on households. Seven (70%) observed that social acceptance of PWDs had gotten better, and many community members were now more supportive than before. Six family respondents (60%) indicated that caregiving remained a heavy burden, especially in cases of hearing, verbal, or intellectual impairments, where direct communication with the PWD was limited. While families appreciated the support from Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal initiatives, they also stressed that assistance was not enough to meet all needs. This suggests that families view empowerment as positive, yet also acknowledge gaps in service coverage.

Persons with disabilities provided the most insightful perspective on the effects of empowerment. Ten out of twelve respondents (83%) said that skill training and employment programs helped them earn independent incomes. Eighty-seven percent (67%) discussed their increasing involvement in community events, decision-making, and social activities. Seven (58%) reported that their self-confidence had improved as a result of empowerment efforts. At the same time, participants identified ongoing barriers, including inaccessible public buildings, transportation issues, and social prejudice. Several PWDs expressed pride in contributing to household income, noting that empowerment strengthened their roles within their families and communities. However, they also recognized that without better policy enforcement and community wide inclusion, complete equality remains out of reach.

The combined findings from departmental representatives, family members and PWDs highlighted empowerment as both a process of individual change and structural transformation. On one hand, PWDs in Jhang reported gains in self reliance, confidence and social participation. Families observed reduced dependency and greater community

acceptance. Departmental representatives acknowledged the effectiveness of their interventions but also pointed to resource and policy limitations. On the other hand, barriers such as stigma, inaccessible infrastructure and insufficient resources continue to hinder progress.

These findings reinforce the importance of an integrated theoretical framework. The Social Model of Disability explains how environmental and attitudinal barriers limit inclusion. The Empowerment Theory describes the personal changes in autonomy and self-confidence reported by PWDs. The CBR framework is reflected in the community-level interventions of the Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal Department. Together, these frameworks demonstrate that empowerment in District Jhang involves not only individual progress but also the transformation of families, institutions and communities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that empowerment has brought significant improvements in the lives of persons with disabilities in District Jhang. PWDs reported greater independence, improved participation in community life and increased ability to earn a living. Families also recognized reduced dependency and more social acceptance. Representatives of the Social Welfare Department emphasized their role in policy implementation and service delivery while also acknowledging barriers such as limited resources and infrastructure gaps. Despite progress, stigma, discrimination and accessibility challenges continue to restrict the full inclusion of PWDs in society.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. In terms of policy and implementation, the government and the Social Welfare & Bait-ul-Maal

Department should enforce the 3% job quota more effectively, allocate greater resources, and strengthen monitoring mechanisms. For economic empowerment, vocational training programs must be expanded, microcredit and self-employment opportunities made available and skill development prioritized. In education and services, inclusive schooling, provision of assistive devices and broader awareness campaigns are necessary to ensure equal opportunities. About gender and social inclusion, special attention should be given to women with disabilities, addressing the multiple forms of discrimination they face while also encouraging broader community acceptance. Finally, coordination and participation need to be enhanced by linking government departments with NGOs, community groups and self-help groups to create sustainable support networks.

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